

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "The Effect of Public Science on Corporate R&D"

Evaluator 1 Ioannis Bournakis¹ David Reinstein

¹SKEMA Business School

Published on: Jun 19, 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.21428/d28e8e57.50ee8ef7>

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ABSTRACT

We organized two evaluations of the paper: "The Effect of Public Science on Corporate R&D"[1]. The first evaluation (anonymous) is highly critical of the paper's identification strategy, citing concerns such as collider bias and endogenous *shares*. The second evaluator (Bournakis) is more positive, finding the results surprising and convincing, suggesting a difference-in-differences robustness check and raising several requests for clarifications and justifications. The authors respond to the critiques in detail, offering a robust public discussion of econometric identification in an applied context. To read these evaluations and the responses, please see the links below.

Evaluations and author response

1. [Evaluator 1](#)
 2. [Ioannis Bournakis](#)
- [Author response](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment (See footnote¹)

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' should this be published in?² *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.*

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Evaluator 1	64	2.8
Ioannis Bournakis	75	3.0 - 4.0

See "[Metrics](#)" below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators' ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).³

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.

Evaluation summaries

Anonymous evaluator 1

The paper provides evidence on a recently relevant issue in science policy: the spillover effects of public science. However, these effects are not well-identified. There are numerous issues likely distorting the identification, including bad controls and a shift-share design with endogenous shares.

Ioannis Bournakis

The paper develops a systematic framework for analysing how public science capital affects corporate R&D, leveraging rich firm-level data and extensive robustness checks to support credible causal inference. My main question is whether this instrumental variables strategy offers clear advantages over a difference-in-differences design.

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator 1		Evaluator 2		
	Anonymous		Ioannis Bournakis		
Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments
Overall assessment ⁴	64	(58, 70)	75	(75, 87)	
Claims, strength, characterization of evidence ⁵	57	(44, 70)	80	(80, 90)	6
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁷	46	(42, 50)	90	(90, 95)	8

Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ⁹	28	(36, 44)	80	(80, 90)	10
Logic & communication ¹¹	68	(62, 74)	65	(65, 83)	12
Open, collaborative, replicable ¹³	65	(62, 68)	85	(75, 85)	14
Real-world relevance ^{15,16}	67	(62, 71)	72	(72, 88)	17
Relevance to global priorities ^{18,} 19	67	(62, 71)	72	(72, 88)	

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1		Evaluator 2		
	Anonymous		Ioannis Bournakis		
Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Comments
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	2.8	(2.4, 3.2)	4.0	(3.5, 4.8)	20

What 'quality journal' do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?	3.6	(3.1, 4.1)	4.2	(4.0, 5.0)	21
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 				

Claim identification and assessment (summary)

For the full discussions, see the corresponding sections in each linked evaluation.

	Main research claim ²²	Belief in claim ²³	Key implication(s) of claims	Suggested robustness checks ²⁴
Evaluator 1 Anonymous	Increased exposure to public invention decreases a firm's private R&D expenditure	I believe neither the sign nor magnitude of this estimated relationship. My prior for this relationship is not swayed by the paper.		N/A
Evaluator 2 Ioannis Bournakis	... ²⁵ [1] substitution versus complementarity ...: a one-standard-deviation increase in university patents reduces corporate patenting by 51%, underscoring the need to carefully calibrate technology-			

<p>transfer and licensing policies.²⁶</p> <p>[2]... embodied human capital in the form of PhD graduates plays a powerful complementary role—each one-standard deviation rise in relevant doctorates yields a 53% boost in firm patents²⁷—highlighting the high leverage of targeted doctoral training initiatives.</p> <p>Third...²⁸ an increase in university patents actually crowds out private patenting²⁹ ...</p>	<p>[Response suggests the evaluator largely believes what they see as the main research claims.]</p> <p>...Before reading this paper, I would have assumed that public knowledge and corporate innovation were largely complementary, with firms’ absorptive capacity determining who benefits from publicly available research. In that view, only frontier firms—or those with sufficient in-house expertise—could effectively incorporate external knowledge. Instead, this study shows that an increase in university patents actually crowds out private patenting, challenging the assumption of universal complementarity. ...</p>	<p>[Continued from previous question...]</p> <p>... Is private innovation output more important to aggregate economic growth than the underlying public knowledge? Based on historical breakthroughs tied to basic research, one could argue that the non-commercialized, foundational discoveries generated by public institutions have a greater long-run impact on growth than the downstream patents produced by firms. If so, the fact that public knowledge displaces some private patenting may not warrant corrective policy; it might simply reflect an optimal division of labor between public basic research and private development.</p>	<p>Implementing a difference-in-differences identification strategy [Full reponse in footnote and report].³⁰</p>
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Evaluation manager’s discussion

I am particularly pleased with the depth of these evaluations, and the authors’ responses. This is a particularly rich public discussion of econometric identification issues in this applied context.

I intend to revisit this section to provide further synthesis and discussion, but I do not want to delay the release of this evaluation package further.³¹

I left a few sidebar notes at various points in the PubPub interface; these should not be interpreted as official Unjournal responses.

Unjournal process notes

We shared [these](#) 'bespoke evaluation notes' (leveraging LLM tools) with the evaluators. These also contain some discussion of our process.

References

1. Arora, A., Belenzon, S., Cioaca, L. C., Sheer, L., & Zhang, H. (2023). The Effect of Public Science on Corporate R&D. NBER Working Paper No. 31899. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w31899>

Footnotes

1. We asked them to rank this paper "heuristically" as a percentile "relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years." We requested they "consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice. [↵](#)
2. See ranking tiers discussed [here](#). [↵](#)
3. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↵](#)

4.

Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

[↵](#)

5. "Do the authors do a good job of (i) stating their main questions and claims, (ii) providing strong evidence and powerful approaches to inform these, and (iii) correctly characterizing the nature of their evidence?"

This was on the newer form only [↵](#)

6. The paper clearly states its primary research question: How do different aspects of public science influence corporate innovation activities? The approach is grounded in a thorough theoretical framework and supported by strong empirical evidence. The empirical strategy addresses potential endogeneity bias between corporate innovation activities and public knowledge, primarily by leveraging political shifts affecting agency R&D budgets. Although tackling (unobserved) endogeneity bias is an extremely challenging task in economics research, the authors' attempt demonstrates a level of credibility that likely outweighs the potential limitations of the chosen approach. Providing results that establish causal inference adds significant value to the paper and strengthens the robustness of its empirical findings. [↵](#)

7.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

⇐

8.

This paper presents a significant and well-executed empirical study examining how public science, in its various dimensions, affects corporate research and development (R&D). The authors distinguish between three key components of public science: abstract knowledge (e.g., scientific publications), human capital (e.g., PhD scientists), and public inventions (e.g., university patents). Their findings that corporate R&D is driven more by embodied knowledge in human capital and inventions than by abstract knowledge itself offers important insights for science policy and innovation management.

The study contributes to our understanding of how knowledge transfer mechanisms operate in practice and challenges conventional wisdom that treats public science primarily as a non-rival, purely spillover-driven input to private innovation. By leveraging firm-level exposure to exogenous shifts in federal R&D budgets tied to political subcommittee composition, the paper advances causal inference in this domain. Its nuanced implications—for example, the crowding-out effect of public invention on corporate R&D—are particularly relevant in an era of increasing university-industry partnerships and policy attention to innovation ecosystems. ⇐

9. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? ⇐

10.

The paper applies an instrumental variables (IV) estimation to identify the causal impacts of public science on corporate innovation. Specifically, it uses a Bartik-style shift-share IV, where the “shifts” are changes in federal agency R&D budgets, expected to represent exogenous shocks driven mainly by the political composition of Congress. The “shares” are firm-specific exposures based on past patenting activity, publications, or dissertation overlaps.

The validity of this instrument depends on the assumption that political shifts in R&D funding are exogenous to firm-specific innovation shocks. Admittedly, this is a reasonable assumption within this context, although the presence of weak identification might persist, particularly for large firms, especially considering spatial dimensions that may be interrelated with the determination of the federal budget. The authors are aware of this concern and address it by controlling for potential firm size effects through the inclusion of lagged R&D stock or annual sales in all relevant specifications. This is convincing and sufficient to argue that the presented results are not significantly biased, especially given the inherent challenges of identifying causal relationships in models of this kind.

Nonetheless, I would like to suggest that the authors consider whether a difference-in-differences (DiD) approach could also be used to address the endogeneity bias between public knowledge and in-house innovation efforts. I do not claim that a DiD approach 2 would necessarily outperform the strategy they have already employed, but it could serve as an additional robustness check. For example, one could identify a subset of firms more exposed to changes in public science funding (e.g., firms active in fields funded by certain agencies) and another subset less exposed, and then compare their innovation outcomes before and after the shocks, assuming the timing of R&D budget changes is exogenous. From the top of my head, one could think of firms heavily linked to NASA subfields versus those linked to the Department of Agriculture. This could be an interesting extension if the firm panel allows for such an analysis.

In any case, the current identification strategy has strong merits and mitigates endogeneity concerns in a reasonable and convincing manner. [↵](#)

11. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? [↵](#)

12.

The goals and questions of the paper are clearly articulated: the authors seek to disentangle the distinct effects of public knowledge, human capital, and public inventions on corporate innovation activities. Key concepts are well defined, and the framework guiding the empirical analysis is transparent and logically developed.

Nonetheless, I have some specific queries that I would like to raise. In Equation 3.1, is the variable r a stock variable (representing cumulative knowledge) or just a flow variable? I am aware that later in the paper, the authors treat public knowledge as a stock variable using the perpetual inventory method, but in the theoretical setup, this is not made explicit. It might be useful for the authors to clarify this point clearly from the very beginning.

Additionally, regarding the function ϕ in the profit maximization problem: could it be subject to constant returns to scale (CRS) instead of diminishing returns to scale (DRS)? The authors implicitly assume that the productivity of investment falls with respect to both human capital and public knowledge. This is my understanding based on the setup of the model in Section 3.1, unless I am missing something. While this is a conventional assumption, would it not also be possible to allow for CRS or even increasing returns to scale (IRS) if the use of new knowledge capital (either internal or external to the firm) generates spillovers that lead to new ideas at a constant or increasing rate? In other words, is there any role for unintended spillovers in the model that could counteract the diminishing returns assumption? This is just a question and may not be crucial for the modelling approach, but it could be worth considering or clarifying.

Furthermore, I was wondering whether the authors included the level dummy for high ability in the regressions of Table 10, since they are using the interaction term between public investment and human capital. Isn't it the case that these regressions should also include the dummy variable itself? Regarding this point, do we need to report the overall effects of the variables of interest (public investment and human capital) in Tables 10 and 11 etc, given that they are interacted with industry fixed effects, especially in Table 11? Also, why does the dependent variable in Tables 10, 11, and 12 include only the time subscript but not the firm subscript? Are we missing something here?

In Section 3.2.4, the authors distinguish between leaders and followers. While the paper specifically focuses on the U.S., I would like to raise a question about whether there could also be a role for a global frontier instead of just a national frontier, as well as the potential impact of international public knowledge capital. The authors have deliberately excluded non-U.S. PhDs from the empirical analysis. This choice merits further justification. Is this decision conceptually meaningful? Is the influence of international public knowledge capital on U.S. corporations truly negligible? Admittedly, U.S. firms are typically positioned at the international technological frontier, but there might be sectors where the U.S. lags behind other countries. Have the authors considered these possibilities?